

Miller

a swiss-army
chainsaw for
CSV and more

csv,conf,v7

```
$ cat example.csv
color,shape,flag,index,quantity,rate
yellow,triangle,1,11,43.6498,9.8870
red,square,1,15,79.2778,0.0130
red,circle,1,16,13.8103,2.9010
red,square,0,48,77.5542,7.4670
purple,triangle,0,51,81.2290,8.5910
red,square,0,64,77.1991,9.5310
purple,triangle,0,65,80.1405,5.8240
yellow,circle,1,73,63.9785,4.2370
yellow,circle,1,87,63.5058,8.3350
purple,square,0,91,72.3735,8.2430
```

```
$ mlr --icsv --oprint sort -f color,shape example.csv
color  shape  flag index quantity rate
purple square  0   91   72.3735  8.2430
purple triangle 0   51   81.2290  8.5910
purple triangle 0   65   80.1405  5.8240
red    circle  1   16   13.8103  2.9010
red    square  1   15   79.2778  0.0130
red    square  0   48   77.5542  7.4670
red    square  0   64   77.1991  9.5310
yellow circle  1   73   63.9785  4.2370
yellow circle  1   87   63.5058  8.3350
yellow triangle 1   11   43.6498  9.8870
```

```
$ mlr --icsv --ojson filter '$color=="yellow"' example.csv
{
  "color": "yellow",
  "shape": "triangle",
  "flag": 1,
  "index": 11,
  "quantity": 43.6498,
  "rate": 9.8870
}
{
  "color": "yellow",
  "shape": "circle",
  "flag": 1,
  "index": 73,
  "quantity": 63.9785,
  "rate": 4.2370
}
{
  "color": "yellow",
  "shape": "circle",
  "flag": 1,
  "index": 87,
  "quantity": 63.5058,
  "rate": 8.3350
}
```

```
$ mlr --c2p --from example.csv put '$qr = $quantity * $rate'
color shape  flag k index quantity rate qr
yellow triangle true 1 11 43.6498 9.8870 431.5655726
red square true 2 15 79.2778 0.0130 1.0306114
red circle true 3 16 13.8103 2.9010 40.063680299999994
red square false 4 48 77.5542 7.4670 579.0972113999999
purple triangle false 5 51 81.2290 8.5910 697.8383389999999
red square false 6 64 77.1991 9.5310 735.7846221000001
purple triangle false 7 65 80.1405 5.8240 466.738272
yellow circle true 8 73 63.9785 4.2370 271.0769045
yellow circle true 9 87 63.5058 8.3350 529.3208430000001
purple square false 10 91 72.3735 8.2430 596.5747605000001
```

John Kerl

Day job: TileDB

Project: <https://tiledb.com/data-types/single-cell> -- joint work with CZI

We're hiring!

Why? And, why Miller?

When you `grep` your `.csv`, I cry -- because **you deserve better**

- `grep`, `cut`, `sort` etc are line-aware and they're good for **lines** and integer column indices: `cut -d, -f 2,3`; `sort -k 7`
- Nacimiento, ~2015: I wanted a **record-aware** tool

```
$ grep purple example.csv
purple,triangle,false,5,51,81.2290,8.5910
purple,triangle,false,7,65,80.1405,5.8240
purple,square,false,10,91,72.3735,8.2430
```

```
$ mlr --csv grep purple example.csv
color,shape,flag,k,index,quantity,rate
purple,triangle,false,5,51,81.2290,8.5910
purple,triangle,false,7,65,80.1405,5.8240
purple,square,false,10,91,72.3735,8.2430
```

```
$ mlr --icsv --opprint filter '$color == "purple"' example.csv
color shape flag k index quantity rate
purple triangle false 5 51 81.2290 8.5910
purple triangle false 7 65 80.1405 5.8240
purple square false 10 91 72.3735 8.2430
```

Many tools are out there

- **xsv** : custom indices, fast
- **zsv** : *really* fast
- **csvtk** : closer to **dplyr**
- **q** : supports SQL
- **jq** : *amazing* tool for JSON
- **nu** : a fully interactive data-aware shell, multiple file formats
- ... and more including (of course!) **pandas**, **datasette**, **frictionless**, ...

Miller (**m**l**r**) is ...

- Multiple **file formats**: CSV, TSV, JSON, JSON Lines, PPRINT, XTAB, DKVP, integer-indexed (like the Unix toolkit)
- Mix of:
 - **sort/cut**/etc equivalents
 - and an **awk**-like programming language
- **Unix-toolkit/Unix-pipe** family tree with **record awareness**
- Streaming/out-of-core/bigger-than-RAM when it can
- Open source, free, single binary without runtime dependencies

Installation

- MacOS, Windows, Linux, BSDs, ...
 - Older distros have older Miller versions
 - Latests: <https://miller.readthedocs.io/en/latest/installing-miller/>
- `brew install miller`
- `choco install miller`
- `yum install miller`
- `apt-get install miller`
- `conda install -c conda-forge miller`

Verbs; functions

Like cut, sort, sed, grep; awk-like DSL

altkv
bar
bootstrap
cat
check
clean-whitespace
count
count-distinct
count-similar
cut
decimate
fill-down
fill-empty
filter
Features which filter shares with put
flatten
format-values
fraction
gap
grep
group-by
group-like
having-fields
head
histogram
join

json-parse
json-stringify
label
latin1-to-utf8
utf8-to-latin1
least-frequent
merge-fields
most-frequent
nest
nothing
put
Features which put shares with filter
regularize
remove-empty-columns
rename
reorder
repeat
reshape
sample
sec2gmt
sec2gmtdate
seqgen
shuffle
skip-trivial-records
sort
sort-within-records
split

stats1
stats2
step
summary
tac
tail
tee
template
top
unflatten
uniq
unspace
unsparsify

Functions by class

- **Arithmetic functions:** bitcount, madd, mexp, mmul, msub, pow, %, &, *, **, +, -, *, .+, .-, ./, /, //, <<, >>, >>>, ^, |, ~.
- **Boolean functions:** !, !=, !=~, &&, <, <=, <=>, ==, =~, >, >=, ?:, ??, ???, ^^, ||.
- **Collections functions:** append, arrayify, concat, depth, flatten, get_keys, get_values, haskey, json_parse, json_stringify, leafcount, length, mapdiff, mapexcept, mapselect, mapsum, unflatten.
- **Conversion functions:** boolean, float, fmtifnum, fmtnum, hexfmt, int, joink, joinkv, joinv, splita, splitax, splitkv, splitkvx, splitnv, splitnvx, string.
- **Hashing functions:** md5, sha1, sha256, sha512.
- **Higher-order-functions functions:** any, apply, every, fold, reduce, select, sort.
- **Math functions:** abs, acos, acosh, asin, asinh, atan, atan2, atanh, cbrt, ceil, cos, cosh, erf, erfc, exp, expm1, floor, invqnorm, log, log10, log1p, logifit, max, min, qnorm, round, roundm, sgn, sin, sinh, sqrt, tan, tanh, urand, urand32, urandelement, urandint, urandrange.
- **String functions:** capitalize, clean_whitespace, collapse_whitespace, format, gssub, gsub, latin1_to_utf8, leftpad, lstrip, regextract, regextract_or_else, rightpad, rstrip, ssub, strip, strlen, sub, substr, substr0, substr1, tolower, toupper, truncate, unformat, unformatx, utf8_to_latin1, ..
- **System functions:** exec, hostname, os, system, version.
- **Time functions:** dhms2fsec, dhms2sec, fsec2dhms, fsec2hms, gmt2localtime, gmt2sec, hms2fsec, hms2sec, localtime2gmt, localtime2sec, sec2dhms, sec2gmt, sec2gmtdate, sec2hms, sec2localdate, sec2localtime, strftime, strftime_local, strptime, strptime_local, systime, systimeint, uptime.
- **Typing functions:** asserting_absent, asserting_array, asserting_bool, asserting_boolean, asserting_empty, asserting_empty_map, asserting_error, asserting_float, asserting_int, asserting_map, asserting_nonempty_map, asserting_not_array, asserting_not_empty, asserting_not_map, asserting_not_null, asserting_null, asserting_numeric, asserting_present, asserting_string, is_absent, is_array, is_bool, is_boolean, is_empty, is_empty_map, is_error, is_float, is_int, is_map, is_nan, is_nonempty_map, is_not_array, is_not_empty, is_not_map, is_not_null, is_null, is_numeric, is_present, is_string, typeof.

Exploring data

Data source: <https://github.com/datablist/sample-csv-files>

- What fields are in the data? (Use XTAB output for wide data)

```
$ mlr --csv head -n 1 organizations-1000000.csv
Index,Organization Id,Name,Website,Country,Description,Founded,Industry,Number of employees
1,74fc6fDadF400Dc,"Wilcox, Griffith and Hawkins",https://tanner.com/,Cape Verde,Horizontal bi-directional artificial intelligence,1971,Professional Training,1550
```

```
$ mlr --icsv --oxtab head -n 1 organizations-1000000.csv
Index          1
Organization Id 74fc6fDadF400Dc
Name           Wilcox, Griffith and Hawkins
Website        https://tanner.com/
Country        Cape Verde
Description     Horizontal bi-directional artificial intelligence
Founded        1971
Industry       Professional Training
Number of employees 1550
```

- How many countries?

```
$ mlr --csv --from organizations-1000000.csv \
> uniq -n -f Country
count
243
```

- How many organizations in Argentina?

- Miller processes *record streams*
- `--csv` or `--icsv --ojson`: same format, or format conversion
- `then` is the pipe between *verbs* (transformations): `mlr -l`
- The `filter` and `put` verbs support a domain-specific language (DSL)
- You can set a `~/ .mlrrc` file with defaults like `--csv`

```
$ mlr --csv --from organizations-1000000.csv \
> uniq -c -f Country \
> then sort -f Country \
> then head
Country,count
Afghanistan,4058
Albania,4001
Algeria,3996
American Samoa,4007
Andorra,4203
Angola,4113
Anguilla,4097
Antarctica (the territory South of 60 deg S),4009
Antigua and Barbuda,4194
Argentina,4070
```

Exploring data

- Smallest Argentinian organizations?

```
$ mlr --icsv --oprint --from organizations-1000000.csv \  
> filter '$Country == "Argentina"' \  
> then cut -xf 'Index,Organization Id,Country' \  
> then sort -n 'Number of employees' \  
> then reorder -f 'Name,Number of employees' \  
> then head
```

Name	Number of employees	Website	Description	Founded	Industry
Bean Group	1	http://www.rocha-moon.com/	Realigned dedicated encoding	2021	Online Publishing
Patton Ltd	4	http://knox-wood.org/	Customizable discrete knowledge user	1986	Veterinary
Hartman-Preston	6	http://dudley.net/	Organic reciprocal moratorium	1976	Capital Markets / Hedge F
Floyd PLC	6	http://www.russell.com/	Optimized modular array	2017	Luxury Goods / Jewelry
Skinner, Mathews and Welch	7	https://www.dudley-malone.com/	Down-sized 5thgeneration core	2008	Marketing / Advertising /
Gallagher, Combs and Acosta	8	https://www.harrell.com/	Sharable high-level solution	2016	Non - Profit / Volunteeri
Villegas and Sons	11	https://www.raymond-montoya.com/	Assimilated user-facing workforce	1995	Commercial Real Estate
Terrell, Malone and Larson	13	https://www.pearson.info/	Centralized didactic time-frame	2002	Health / Fitness
Mcbride PLC	15	https://www.mejia.org/	Total 24hour info-mediaries	2002	Design
Pham Inc	18	http://www.campos-dennis.com/	Customer-focused multi-tasking analyzer	1974	Import / Export

- New fields, and JSON output

```
$ mlr --icsv --ojson --from organizations-1000000.csv \  
> filter '$Country == "Argentina"' \  
> then cut -xf 'Country' \  
> then put '$provenance = {  
>   "conference": "csv,conf,v7", "when":sec2gmt(systime()),  
> }' \  
> > output.json  
$  
$ ls -l output.json  
-rw-r--r--  1 johnkerl  staff  1485111 Apr 15 17:15 output.json
```

```
$ mlr --json head -n 2 output.json  
[  
{  
  "Index": 50,  
  "Organization Id": "C3eEfd5aAbBE5E7",  
  "Name": "Rush-Hurley",  
  "Website": "https://harris-koch.biz/",  
  "Description": "Customizable cohesive architecture",  
  "Founded": 1976,  
  "Industry": "Non - Profit / Volunteering",  
  "Number of employees": 9677,  
  "provenance": {  
    "conference": "csv,conf,v7",  
    "when": "2023-04-15T21:15:26Z"  
  }  
},  
{  
  "Index": 1275,  
  "Organization Id": "2566cf3BECC5F3f",  
  "Name": "Duarte-Berry",  
  "Website": "https://key-spence.com/",  
  "Description": "Triple-buffered intangible paradigm",  
  "Founded": 1987,  
  "Industry": "Market Research",  
  "Number of employees": 9323
```

Community

Ayuda / apoyo / servicio

- `man mlr` and `mlr help`
- <https://miller.readthedocs.io>
- <https://github.com/johnkerl/miller/issues>
- <https://github.com/johnkerl/miller/discussions>
- <https://github.com/johnkerl/miller/discussions/1268> -- this talk
- Se necesita ayuda: lots of open feature requests (Go language)
 - Miller is open source and development time is the most precious commodity

Discuss

↑ 1

↑ 1

↑ 1

↑ 1

↑ 1

↑ 1

↑ 1

 How to use environment variables for field name in DSL?
YokojimaSkewers started on Feb 25 in General

 Can Miller remove records?
YokojimaSkewers asked on Feb 28 in Q&A · **Answered**

 How can I right pad an integer with zeros?
derekmahar asked on Dec 19, 2022 in Q&A · **Answered**

 strptime support for non zero-padded values?
archetyped asked on Feb 22 in Q&A · **Answered**

NAME

 5
Miller -- like awk, sed, cut, join, and sort for name-indexed data such as CSV and t

SYNOPSIS

 1
Usage: `mlr [flags] {verb} [verb-dependent options ...] {zero or more file names}`

If zero file names are provided, standard input is read, e.g.
`mlr --csv sort -f shape example.csv`

Output of one verb may be chained as input to another using "then", e.g.
`mlr --csv stats1 -a min,mean,max -f quantity then sort -f color example.csv`

Please see 'mlr help topics' for more information. Please also see <https://miller.r>

Questions?

Bonus slide: Data cleaning

Limpieza de datos

- (+) Miller has many verbs and functions for data cleaning
 - See also the [data-cleaning examples page](#)
- (-) It's a bit fussy about [RFC 4180](#)
 - Pro-tip: on parse failure, also try `--csvlite`
 - In the C implementation (Miller ≤ 5) I had a hand-written CSV parser
 - In the Go implementation I use the Go library's CSV parser -- better for me to revert to manual

Bonus slide: JSON processing

Ahorrando dinero con Miller

Here's one of a few shell aliases I use to manage my instances

Together with a starter and a stopper alias -- my boss likes this!

```
show-instance() {  
  aws ec2 describe-instances --query "Reservations[0].Instances[0]" --instance-ids "$1" \  
  | mlr --ijson --oxtab \  
  cut -o -f KeyName,InstanceType,InstanceId,Architecture,LaunchTime,Placement.AvailabilityZone,State  
}
```

```
$ show-instance i-00f220b2c18431cb8  
KeyName      kerl  
InstanceType m5.4xlarge  
InstanceId   i-00f220b2c18431cb8  
Architecture x86_64  
LaunchTime   2023-04-14T12:38:16+00:00  
State.Code   16  
State.Name   running
```

```
$ stop-instance i-00f220b2c18431cb8  
{  
  "StoppingInstances": [  
    {  
      "CurrentState": {  
        "Code": 64,  
        "Name": "stopping"  
      },  
      "InstanceId": "i-00f220b2c18431cb8",  
      "PreviousState": {  
        "Code": 16,  
        "Name": "running"  
      }  
    }  
  ]  
}
```